

THE IMPACT OF HAPPY MUSIC ON THE BEHAVIOUR OF INDIVIDUALS FOR BUSINESS ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract:

This study is an interdisciplinary study that examines the research and discourse of music and business organizations, music is the essential part of our life now. It becomes the universal language for all the inhabitants of this world and no one can deny the powerful effects of music in this new era the present study has a significant contribution to the existing literature with its contribution in the form of the impact of the happy music on the behavior of the individual. This study aimed how happy music can be used as an intervention to improve productivity, innovation, creativity, and cost efficiency and increase job satisfaction. The focus of the present study is only on the impact of happy music on the behaviour of employees in the business organization. Happy Music has observed to be a language of emotions and feelings. The musical power can alter anyone's mood the modification of mood is directly related to the experiences and the related feelings. The resultant outcome of this attachment is measurable and physically observable; tears, laughter, sadness, happiness, shivers, relaxation and thrills are some examples of these emotional experiences. The recommendation is the need to care about music because it affects the behavior of individuals and gives a greater incentive for administrative production.

Keywords: impact of happy music, behaviour of individuals, business organizations

1. Introduction

Music is the essential part of our life nowadays. If we look back into our history then we came to know that our forefathers have a rich treasure in their daily life in the form of

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music (Kemper & Danhauer, 2005) Music becomes the universal language for all the inhabitants of this world and no one can deny the powerful effects of music in this new era (Halstead & Roscoe, 2002). A typical path for individuals to relax and decrease stress or apprehension is listening to music (Emery, Hsiao, Hill, & Frid, 2003). A few studies have demonstrated that subjective execution can be a raised by bringing ambient background music into the work environment, in spite of the fact that others have created about indicating performance to be disabled (Szabo, Ainsworth, & Danks, 2005). Satisfaction of the employees has a crucial importance in any business or any other organization. Only satisfied employees can take the business to the height where it should be. Productivity, creativity and innovations all come from the satisfaction of the employees (Lesiuk, 2005).

The modern technology makes it easy to measure the satisfaction of the employees. Every year businesses spend a reasonable amount of their budget to satisfy their employees and the other things that can improve, increase and facilitate their satisfaction level. The most effective way to satisfy the employees is to analyze the ways and things that affect their mood, behavior and intentions while they are working in the organizations. The positive mood brings more satisfaction in the behavior of the employee in the shape of pleasant and relaxed working environment (Landy & Conte, 2016). The positive and negative mood has seen a direct effect on the productivity of the employees.

1.1 Previous Studies

The conflict of positive and negative influences of listening to music and its influences on the employees' performance has a very long debate in which the supporters of listening to music recommended some suggestions that if applied to the organizations has more benefits for the employees and organizations itself (Wakefield, Wakefield, Baker, & Wang, 2011), The power of music is that it influences the emotions, feelings and minds of the people, so the relaxation music touches their mind and relaxes their nerves; in result, the productivity lowers down with this type of music on the job (Deng & Poole, 2010), The conflict of positive and negative influences of listening to music and its influences on the employees' performance has a very long debate in which the supporters of listening to music recommended some suggestions that if applied to the organizations has more benefits for the employees and organizations itself (Wakefield et al., 2011), The result of this study proves that there is a significant influence on the performance of employees when they listened to music and when they do not listen to music. The background music has been experimented with playing a different type of music at different times and again the performance measures were recorded, the study suggests that the background music should be changed according to the situation in the organization (Lesiuk, 2005).

1.2 Research Methods - Survey

As the objectives and hypotheses of the study determined that it is a quantitative study that seeks responses from a large number of respondents with different backgrounds.

The study has used two different questionnaires to collect the data. Later, descriptive statistics have been used to analyze the data.

1.3 Sampling Strategy

The study depends on the primary data to test the hypotheses and used two of questionnaires to collect the data from Libya. The data has been collected through two questionnaires as follows:

1. The students of Higher Institute of Arts Technology in Tripoli, Libya.
2. Administrative Staff at the Higher Institute of Arts Technology in Tripoli, Libya.

The two different sample groups have been selected to help generalize the results as one group consists of students of Higher Institute of Arts Technology in Tripoli, Libya and the second sample group consists of administrative staff from the same institute. Moreover, the two groups provide distinct insights as one group consists of students (usually are young, and have different tastes and time listening to music), however, the professionals have a bit higher age group with limited time listening to music.

1.4 Sample Size and Technique

It is essential to choose the sample size for any study, therefore, for the purpose of this study a sample of 280 respondents has been selected for the questionnaire for administrative staff at the Higher Institute of Arts Technology in Tripoli, Libya; the second questionnaire has 400 respondents and is students from Higher Institute of Arts Technology in Tripoli, Libya. The searcher did that face to face at the Higher Institute of Arts Technology in Tripoli, Libya. Also, there is a difference in the number of students and staff, which proves that the number of students more than the number of employees.

It is pertinent to mention here that convenience sampling has been used to select the sample of the study which states “it is a non-probability sampling technique where subjects are selected because of their convenient accessibility and proximity to the researcher. As the sampling technique was convenience sampling, thus, the questionnaire for students was served to 400 students the response rate from the students was 53%, out of which only 50% responses were valid there are only 200 valid responses from students. As far as the questionnaire for administrative staff, the response rate was almost 90%—there

Table 1.1: Music Influence on Job Satisfaction

		Frequency	Percent (%)	Valid Percent (%)
Valid	Music made me feel more satisfied than silence	150	60.0	60.0
	Music is no different than silence on satisfaction	62	24.8	24.8
	Music made me feel less satisfied than silence	38	15.2	15.2
	Total	250	100%	100%

Figure 1.1: Music Influence on Job Satisfaction

Sixty percent (60%) of the respondents stated that the music they listen significantly influence on job satisfaction (how satisfied you are with your job at lunch and at the end of the day), while 24.8% respondents indicated that music has no difference than silence on satisfaction, whereas 15.2% stated that music made them felt less satisfied than silence.

Table 1.2: Favorite Music

		Frequency	Percent (%)	Valid Percent (%)
Valid	Happy Music	128	51.2	51.2
	Music of Islamic events	42	16.8	16.8
	Sad Music	22	8.8	8.8
	Other Music	58	23.2	23.2
	Total	250	100%	100%

Figure 1.2: Favorite Music

51.2% respondents indicated that they listen to happy music, 23.2% respondents specify the category of other music, while 16.8% opted for soul music. However, there are 8.8% respondents indicated the sad music is their choice. The findings clearly show that more than half of the respondents prefer to listen happy music. In order to test the hypotheses, there are several findings that provide the basis for particular support for three hypotheses. The data analysis from the questionnaires provided several findings.

2. Discussion

In order to test the hypotheses, there are several findings that provide the basis for particular support for three hypotheses. The data analysis from the questionnaires provided several findings 39.6% respondents indicate that they are music enthusiasts, and enjoy listening to various genres of music on a daily basis whereas 37.6% respondents showed interest in the specific type of music they enjoy on daily basis. Moreover, 22.8% respondents indicate that they barely listen to music. Therefore, the findings are interesting because 22.8% respondents barely listen to music in my sample.

3. Conclusion and Recommendations

The focus of the present study is solely on the impact of music on the behavior of employees and students in the business organization. According to Fiske (1996), music has observed to be a language of emotions and feelings. The musical power can alter anyone's mood; the alterations of mood are directly related to the experiences and the related feelings when someone is listening to the music. In the same explanation, some scholars said that these alterations of mood swings are because of the previous emotional attachment of individuals that they relate it to the music (Lesiuk, 2005). Individuals feel an emotional attachment, past experiences and beliefs with the musical tone- rhythm when they listen to music. The resultant outcome of this attachment is measurable and physically observable; tears, laughter, sadness, happiness, shivers, relaxation and thrills are some examples of these emotional experiences.

The recommendations are the need to care about music because it affects the behavior of individuals and gives a greater incentive for administrative production.

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